

D4.15 Report from thematic meeting II

Webinar on practical use of NGS

WP4

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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D4.15 REPORT FROM THEMATIC MEETING II WEBINAR ON PRACTICAL USE OF NGS

WP4 (subtask 4.3.3) is responsible for arranging annual thematic integrative meetings (TIMs) between Joint Research Projects and/or Joint Integrative Projects. The aim is to facilitate integration across domains, but within themes, addressing specific thematic integrative needs and opportunities. In 2019, the first TIM was arranged in conjunction with the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting and titled “Data management and digital innovation”. This second TIM was held as a webinar on 29 April 2020 (9.30-12.00 CET) using the Zoom platform. The OHEJP Communication team assisted in the use of this platform.

Subject: The practical use of NGS

Theme: Analytical methods

Organisers: Robert Söderlund, SVA (robert.soderlund@sva.se) and Karin Lagesen, NVI (Karin.Lagesen@vetinst.no), with support from CommsTeam (UoS)

Target group: Epidemiologists, bioinformaticians, microbiologists, and stakeholders

Participants: 79

The invitation was sent to the OHEJP Scientific Steering Board (SSB) and project leaders on April 16 2020. EFSA, ECDC, JPI-AMR and JAMRAI were also informed about and invited to the webinar.

Program

Topic 1: Getting from raw NGS data to outbreak detection

Speakers:

Dr. Hanna Skarin, Director of EURL-Campylobacter, SVA, Uppsala, Sweden

Dr. Nicolas Radomski, ANSES, Paris, France

coffee break

Topic 2: The future roles of NGS data producers and data collectors/users

Speakers:

Dr. Mirko Rossi, EFSA, Parma, Italy

Prof. Tine Hald, DTU, Copenhagen, Denmark

Objective

The webinar aimed to bring OHEJP project members together to discuss the practical application of NGS technologies for molecular epidemiology applications e.g. research, surveillance and outbreak investigation. Encouraging discussion between specialists in different fields was a key objective.

Content

Dr. Skarin presented data from NGS proficiency tests carried out by the EURLs and discussed how the quality of raw sequence data and the assembly influences the interpretation and comparability of typing results. Dr. Radomski from ANSES presented the work his group has done on using statistical methods

for defining isolates as part of an outbreak or not, and how the choice of typing method based on NGS data affects the end result. A discussion followed on the quality control of NGS data and the usefulness of the currently available sequencing technologies for various forms of typing e.g. the widely used cgMLST technique.

The second session started with Prof. Hald from DTU presenting the use of genome data from a “user” perspective, describing how NGS data benefits epidemiological investigations and the promising field of molecular source attribution. Dr. Rossi from EFSA discussed the advantages of the two strategies of collecting data for central analysis or building local capacity for analysis and collecting the results from the perspective of tracing foodborne outbreaks in Europe. A discussion on the topic of how to best collect and store data including metadata followed.

The full webinar was recorded and is available here:

https://surrey-ac.zoom.us/rec/share/5pVMMOmv529ORJGT5WPZYIICPJ7paaa82yUbq_YKyBtJs7FpK9o_yZ6WtwY4Fgdn

Password: 8N?7*\$d0

See the Annex for presentations.

Evaluation

NGS is a key topic for the OHEJP and the field in general, and interest in this event was very high. We note that in a survey to guide the decision to go ahead with the event a number of potential participants said that they could not attend due to technical and other difficulties related to the pandemic. However, the overwhelming majority were in favour of proceeding as planned. The mix of speakers turned out good and provided different perspectives, perhaps giving participants with different backgrounds openings for raising their questions. Having people write their questions in the chat for the moderator to read was a good concept for handling a discussion over Zoom with this many participants. In general the Zoom format worked well and the possibility to record was very welcome given the circumstances. A drawback is that it is difficult to make a complete participant list as not all participants used their full names when signing in.

The relationship between genetic markers of antibiotic resistance identified in genome sequencing data and resistance phenotypes, i.e. the reliability of genome-based resistance testing was suggested by OH-EJP project members as a discussion topic, but could not be addressed in the final program due to time constraints. This topic could be discussed in a future activity.

The question of data comparability between the major sequencing technologies was discussed during the webinar and this discussion has continued between participants afterwards. Together with other factors such as quality control and initial processing of raw data this appears to have the potential to strongly influence conclusions drawn, and several OH-EJP projects would likely benefit from some form of agreed-upon best practice.

Attendance list

Vera Manageiro	INSA
Antoine Drapeau	ANSES
Teresa Vicenza	ISS
Jakub Zajac	?
Christin Wallstab	BfR
Tine Hald	DTU
Tasja Buschhardt	BfR

Célia Leão	INIAV
Giovanni Ianiro	ISS
Ingrid Friesema	RIVM
Jade Passey	U. of Surrey
Rebecca Guy	PHE
Laura Soliani	IZSLER
Abakabir-Mahamat Abdelrahim	ANSES
Cindy Dierikx	RIVM
Gaia Scavia	ISS
Teresa Nogueira	INIAV
Mostafa Abdel,	FLI
Maria Francesca Iulietto	EFSA/RIVM
Valeria Michelacci	ISS
Diana Connor	SSI
Anne Brisabois	ANSES
Federica Palma	ANSES
Lucie Collineau	?
Maria Hellmér	SFA
Mia Torpdahl	SSI
Bavo Verhaegen	Sciensano
Matthias Filter	BfR
Julien Fumey	?
Rosangela Tozzoli	ISS
Tom Van Nieuwenhuysen	?
Manuela Canica	INSA
Susanne Pinto	?
Guido Cordoni	U. of Surrey
Nicolas Radomski	ANSES
Karin Artursson	SVA
Robin Diddens	RIVM
Ilaria Dibartolo	ISS
Mery Pina	I. Pasteur
Robert Söderlund	SVA
Kerstin Stingl	BfR
Monica Ricão	SFA
Ariane Pietzka	AGES
Marina Morganti	IZSLER
Mia Nykvist	SVA
Francesco Pomilio	IZS
Mike Brouwer	WUR
Carlus Deneke	BfR
Dariusz Wasyl	PIWet
Charlotte Valat	ANSES
Virginia Filipello	IZSLER
Vojta Kolacek	?
Janine Heise	GMX
Adriana Cabal Rosel	AGES
Nadja Karamehmedovic	PHA
Karin Lagesen	NVI
Mirko Rossi	EFSA
Julia Bartsch	BfR
Víctor Lorente Leal	VISAVET
Hanna Skarin	SVA
Laurent Guillier	ANSES
Ana Botelho	INIAV
Hanne Debergh	Sciensano
Sylvain Brisse	I. Pasteur
Thomas Haverkamp	NVI
Sven Maurischat	BfR

Kirsten Mooijman	RIVM
Simon Tausch	BfR
Luca de Sabato	ISS
Catarina Flink	SFA
Chiara Bracchi	IZSLER
Koenraad Van Hoorde	Sciensano
Renaud Lailler	ANSES
Dré Kampfraath	WUR
Magdalena Zając	PIWet
Pikka Jokelainen	SSI
Joost Hordijk	RIVM
Stefano Pongolini	IZSLER
Clara Samper Cativiela	UCM